

TEACHER AS FACILITATOR – THE CHANGING ROLE OF THE TEACHER AND ITS IMPACT ON LEARNER AUTONOMY

Bakhriddinov Makhamadali Madaminjon ugli

Turan International university

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Abstract

This thesis explores the evolving role of the teacher as a facilitator in a student-centered B1 language classroom, focusing on how this shift impacts learner autonomy. It examines the traditional versus modern roles of educators, highlighting the pedagogical transformation required to foster an autonomous learning environment. Techniques such as scaffolding, individualized feedback, and facilitating peer interactions are discussed to illustrate how teachers can create a supportive atmosphere conducive to learner-centered education. The research argues that by empowering students and stepping into the role of facilitators, teachers can effectively promote learner independence, engagement, and competence development.

Key words: Facilitator, Learner Autonomy, Student-Centered Classroom, B1 Learners, Scaffolding, Individualized Feedback, Peer Interaction, Collaborative Learning, Self-Assessment, Language Acquisition.

Introduction

In a traditional classroom setting, teachers are often viewed as the primary source of knowledge, and students as passive recipients. However, with the shift toward student-centered learning, particularly for B1 language learners, the teacher's role has transformed into that of a facilitator. This change has implications for how learners engage with content, collaborate with peers, and take ownership of their learning journey. This thesis discusses the evolving role of the teacher from instructor to facilitator and explores how this shift promotes learner autonomy in a student-centered B1 classroom.

The Student-Centered Approach and Its Demands on Teachers

The student-centered approach requires teachers to move away from a lecture-based model to a role that emphasizes guidance, support, and enabling students to take control of their own learning. For B1 language learners—those at an intermediate level—this approach encourages engagement in the learning process, fostering the ability to apply language skills in diverse communicative contexts.

In this model, teachers are no longer the sole dispensers of knowledge but rather serve as facilitators who guide the learning process, encouraging students to explore and discover new concepts independently or collaboratively. This paradigm shift necessitates a change in classroom practices, wherein teachers focus more on fostering skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and effective communication, all while allowing students to play an active role in decision-making related to their learning.

Techniques for Facilitating Learner Autonomy

1. Scaffolding

- Scaffolding is a key strategy used by teachers to support students in their learning process. For B1 learners, this means providing just enough assistance to help them progress without removing the challenge from the task. The role of the facilitator is to adjust the level of support based on the learner's proficiency, gradually removing it as the learner becomes more

competent. This technique not only supports learning but also builds learners' confidence to tackle tasks independently.

2. **Providing Individualized Feedback**

- Individualized feedback is crucial in a student-centered classroom. As facilitators, teachers provide feedback that is specific to each learner's needs, focusing on areas for improvement while acknowledging strengths. This personalized approach helps B1 learners understand their progress, identify areas for further practice, and set realistic goals, ultimately enhancing their ability to regulate their learning.

3. **Facilitating Peer Interaction and Collaborative Learning**

- In the role of facilitator, teachers also focus on creating opportunities for peer interaction. Pair and group work are common activities in a B1 language classroom, allowing students to learn from each other and develop language skills through authentic communication. Teachers guide these interactions by setting clear objectives, monitoring progress, and providing support when necessary. Such collaborative tasks encourage learners to take responsibility for their contributions, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability.

4. **Encouraging Self-Assessment and Goal Setting**

- Facilitators encourage students to assess their own work, helping them become aware of their progress and areas needing improvement. Self-assessment tools, such as checklists or reflective journals, enable learners to take an active role in evaluating their skills. Additionally, setting individual goals is a powerful way to foster autonomy, as it empowers learners to take charge of their learning paths.

Impact on Learner Autonomy

The transformation of the teacher's role from instructor to facilitator directly contributes to the development of learner autonomy. When teachers provide learners with the tools, strategies, and opportunities to take ownership of their learning, they help them build self-efficacy and independence. For B1 learners, this autonomy is particularly beneficial as it encourages them to use the language beyond the confines of the classroom, applying it in real-world contexts, thus deepening their learning experience.

Learner autonomy involves not only the ability to make decisions about one's learning but also the confidence and motivation to take those steps. The facilitator role is crucial in nurturing this mindset, as teachers encourage students to become active participants rather than passive recipients. This leads to an increased sense of responsibility, greater motivation, and ultimately more effective language acquisition.

Changes and solutions

Despite its advantages, adopting the facilitator role can be challenging. Teachers may struggle with relinquishing control, particularly if they are accustomed to traditional methods. Additionally, learners may initially resist taking more responsibility, especially if they are unfamiliar with this approach. To address these challenges, teacher training and professional development are essential to help educators adapt to their new roles. Furthermore, a gradual introduction of student-centered practices can help learners become more comfortable with taking charge of their learning.

Conclusion

The role of the teacher as a facilitator in a student-centered B1 classroom is a critical factor in promoting learner autonomy. By shifting away from traditional teaching methods and

embracing a role that focuses on guiding and empowering learners, teachers can help B1 students become more independent, motivated, and engaged in their language learning journey. This transformation not only supports language competence but also equips learners with the skills necessary for lifelong learning. As facilitators, teachers play a pivotal role in creating a supportive and enabling environment that encourages learners to take ownership of their education.

Glossary

- **Facilitator:** A teacher who guides and supports students in the learning process rather than directly instructing them.
- **B1 Learners:** Intermediate-level language learners, according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR).
- **Scaffolding:** An educational technique in which a teacher provides temporary support to help students achieve a goal, gradually reducing assistance as students become more competent.
- **Learner Autonomy:** The capacity of learners to take control of their learning, including setting goals, monitoring progress, and reflecting on outcomes.
- **Self-Assessment:** The process by which learners evaluate their own work or performance, identifying strengths and areas for improvement.

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